

RELATIONSHIP AGE, GENDER AND OCCUPATION OF CORONA PATIENTS WITH COVID-19 DISEASE INFECTION.

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Abstract

Background: To assist public health strategies in the COVID-19 pandemic, it appears that identifying risk factors for negative outcomes is required. Among these are individual factors, such as age, gender, residence and occupation. A relationship between coronavirus disease and the different conditions has been reported. Although COVID-19 affects all age groups, both gender, different residence area and different professions of people. **Aim:** To understand the relationship between Coronavirus-19 infection and some risk factors. On the other hand, the most common symptoms among people with corona. **Method:** Using the data analysis obtained in electronic health records from hospitals and health centers in the province. **Results:** The results showed that the males are more affected than females and the age group of 21-50 years is the most exposed to infection with the Corona virus. People who live in the rural areas and children are less likely to be infected. Finally, the research indicated that the patient's temperature was raised above 38, which was the most important symptom of the disease.

Key words: risk factor, COVID-19 symptoms, gender, occupation, Residence.

Introduction:

Covid infection 2019 (COVID-19) is the illness brought about by the serious intense respiratory condition Covid 2 (SARS-CoV-2). COVID-19's severity can range from mild to severe in clinical settings, resulting in death in certain individuals. ⁽¹⁾ Transmission of this disease is extremely fast from one man to another however it saw that a loads of variations of case casualty among sex and sexual orientation, ⁽²⁾ as high passing rate in men when contrasted with ladies ⁽³⁾ It saw that there exists an age distinction among the defenseless patients as those patients having constant illness are more inclined to COVID-19 disease than more youthful and moderately aged casualties ⁽⁴⁾ other than this among the youngsters this contamination announced more uncommon as expectations say that kids confined and less open air exercises yet cushion yet pediatric cases might cost if these limitation is elevated ⁽⁵⁾.

Atomic examinations have uncovered that there are some different reasons that youngsters are less vulnerable to disease than the elderly folks they have depicted a relationship between

development factor and infection receptors ⁽⁶⁾. Proof shows that the general death pace of COVID-19 is 3.77–5.4% ⁽⁷⁾. in any case, it increments up to 41.1–61.5% among serious or fundamentally sick patients ⁽⁸⁾. Recognizing the risk variables linked to sickness severity and mortality in COVID19 patients is crucial for lowering the overall death rate. Previous research has found that older age, basic comorbidities, a high D-dimer level, and anomalies in a few biochemical parameters are all strongly linked to the severity of COVID-19 patients' illnesses, including death. ⁽⁹⁾ COVID-19 has a wide clinical spectrum, ranging from asymptomatic upper aviation route illness to severe pneumonia with respiratory failure. Fever, hacking, drowsiness, and dyspnea are all common COVID-19 side effects ⁽¹⁰⁾. Patients with COVID-19 display normal indications that can be partitioned into two gatherings: precise problems and respiratory issues. Methodical problems incorporate fever, migraine and gastrointestinal pain, while respiratory issues incorporate hack, dyspnoea, reciprocal ground-glass opacities and pneumonia ⁽¹¹⁾. Distinguishably, COVID-19 showed some unshared indications with beta-COVID sicknesses like wheezing and rhinorrhea ^(1, 12). The quick spread and extension of SARS-CoV-2 lies on the asymptomatic transporters since they unconsciously send the infection to others ⁽¹³⁾. SARS-CoV-2 is a RNA infection with a genomic size of around 30 kb and sorted under the beta-COVID genera under the coronaviridae family ⁽¹⁴⁾. The regular host repository for SARS-CoV-2 is accepted to be bats as the original infection was found to have 96% grouping comparability with bat's coronavirus ⁽¹⁵⁾.

People might confront extreme fiasco if legitimate mindfulness isn't given to non-industrial nations like Iraq where wellbeing offices are not as in created nations. The motivation behind this review is to distinguish the weakest individuals for shield them from the pestilence.

Methodology: A statistical study based on data obtained from health centers in the governorate and its hospitals.

Statistical Analysis: Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software (version 25.0; IBM, Armonk, NY, USA) was used to analyze the statistics of the variables were expressed as number. In this study, we analyzed data from 3040 patients were diagnosed with Coronavirus, without excluding any case. The period of this study was from April, 2020 to September, 2020. Chi-squared tests were utilized. The p-value for statistical significance was set to 0.0001 in all situations.

Results:

A total of (N=3040) patients with COVID-19 or positive results have been included during the study period, according to gender distribution 63.2% from patients were males and 36.8 % were females, this result showed a statistically significant difference (P=0.0001) between both genders, and reflects the susceptibility of males to the disease is greater than females, as shown in the Table 1.

Table 1- Association gender of patients with COVID-19 infection.

		Frequency	Percent	Chi-Square (df)	p-value
Gender	Male	1921 ^a	63.2	211.580 (1)	0.0001

	Female	1119	36.8		
	Total	3040	100.0		

Also of the total (N = 3040), 70.6% of study participants (27.0%) were between 21 to 30 years old, (23.3%) were between 31 to 40 years old and (20.3%) were between 41 to 50 years old had significantly more effect in corona infection than the other age groups. these differences were higher significant (p=0.0001) compared with the age groups that between 1 to 20 years old and between 51 to 90 years old as in Table 2.

Table 2- Association age groups of patients with COVID-19 infection.

		Frequency	Percent	Chi-Square (df)	p-value
Age Groups (year)	1-10	44	1.5	2214.499 (8)	0.0001
	11-20	156	5.1		
	21-30	818 ^a	27.0		
	31-40	705 ^a	23.3		
	41-50	616 ^a	20.3		
	51-60	379	12.5		
	61-70	208	6.9		
	71-80	79	2.6		
	81-90	25	0.8		
	Total	3030	100.0		

Around (83.1%) of the participants were live in Urban area and (16.9%) were live in Rural area. Significant association was found between Residence of patients and COVID-19 infection. These results shown in Table 3.

Table 3- Association Residence of patients with COVID-19 infection.

		Frequency	Percent	Chi-Square (df)	p-value
Residence	Rural	513	16.9	1325.418 (1)	0.0001
	Urban	2517 ^a	83.1		
	Total	3030	100.0		

As shown in Table 4. Among these occupation categories, affiliated health (18.5%) was the highest category infected with corona virus and the patients who do not belong to any of these categories (28.0%) (others). Compared with the rest of ranks (Child, Housewife, Earner, Student, Military and Employees in state institutions, the differences were highly significant (p=0.0001).

Table 4- Association occupation of patients with COVID-19 infection.

		Frequency	Percent	Chi-Square (df)	p-value

Occupation	Child	22	0.7	1324.515 (7)	0.0001
	Housewife	472	15.7		
	Earnar	466	15.5		
	Student	106	3.5		
	Military	202	6.7		
	health worker	557 ^a	18.5		
	Employees in state institutions	343	11.4		
	Others	844 ^a	28.0		
	Total	3030	100.0		

On the other hand, the most important symptoms that appear on Corona patients were Fever (19%), headache (14%) and Emaciation (13.1%). While Cough (13%), breathing difficulty (11%), pharyngeal heartburn (8.9%), Confusion (5.9%), Runny nose (4.8%), Nausea and vomiting (3.6%), diarrhea (3.4%) Symptoms appeared at a lower rate, and the less noticeable symptoms in this study were A symptom (1.8%), banging and frenzy (0.3%) and Bluish (0.3%) as shown in Table 5 and Fig 1.

Table 5- Symptoms of COVID-19 disease.

		Frequency	Percent	Chi-Square (df)	p-value
Symptoms	Fever	448 ^a	19.0%	1339.82 (12)	0.0001
	pharyngeal heartburn	210	8.9%		
	Cough	306	13.0%		
	Breathing difficulty	280	11.9%		
	Runny nose	114	4.8%		
	Emaciation	308 ^a	13.1%		
	Diarrhea	80	3.4%		
	Headache	330 ^a	14.0%		
	Nausea and vomiting	84	3.6%		
	banging and frenzy	6	0.3%		
	Bluish	6	0.3%		
	Confusion	138	5.9%		
	A symptom	42	1.8%		
	Total	2352	100.0%		

Figure -1 COVID-19 symptoms percentage

Discussion:

The current review was conducted to evaluate the information on COVID-19 infection and its relationship with age, gender, occupation, and residence of patients. This review revealed that men are more affected by coronavirus than women, this result was confirmed by **Langer and his colleagues** ⁽¹⁶⁾ who found that females are less likely to contract the disease compared to males. Unlike females, males are more likely to die from COVID-19 and will have worse clinical outcomes in general. Among the social factors that add to this gender gap are gender discrepancies in the potential for preoccupation with work environment contacts essential to the spread of irresistible infection transmitted by the respiratory or close-contact course for example, COVID-19 was also observed as a lifestyle, 95.4% of male patients were not active while female only 89.3% were not. In the continuous pandemic it seen that sex and sex related elements apply a critical effect. Another factor of heterogeneity in deaths due to COVID19 is gender as there are significant differences between the sexes with higher risks in men than women ⁽¹⁷⁾. Which may have something to do with sex hormones such as testosterone and estrogen which appear to be essential in conditioning the body's immune response and the presence of other danger factors, for example diabetes, high blood pressure and cardiovascular disease, that affect men more than women. The study showed the age group of 21-50 years were the most affected group by the Corona virus compared to the younger groups or older groups. although studies have shown that the spread of COVID-19 infection is more popular in older people than in younger individuals ⁽¹⁸⁾. Additionally, due to children's frequent exposure to respiratory infections and an extensive immunization regimen, their bodies have trained immunity that may help them fight infection better than older adults ⁽¹⁹⁾. Furthermore, the worst outcomes linked with aging may be influenced by intrinsic pathophysiological changes in the respiratory system, as well as the increased occurrence of chronic comorbidities as people become older ⁽²⁰⁾. However, it is important to

evaluate chronological age in isolation, without taking into account the fact that humans do not age and that the essential instruments of maturation may differ across individuals.

The results showed that living in the countryside reduces the incidence of infection as in the light of a study that revealed the lifestyle of people, it was noted that the lifestyle of peasants in rural and urban areas is diverse. Villagers are really more active as compared to individuals who live in cities or urban communities. 18% of the villagers are really active while 10% and 7% of the city and town population were active ⁽²¹⁾. These study confirmed that the patient's occupation is related to exposure to COVID-19 infection. As a result, employment has been viewed as a critical factor in the risk of infection ⁽²²⁾. COVID-19 outbreaks have been linked to a variety of sectors, to be honest. Laborers in jobs where physical separation from colleagues, consumers, and patients is difficult, as well as representatives executing work exercises in indoor settings or with shared transportation or convenience may have a larger risk of infection if no control measures are in place ⁽²³⁾. On the other hand, as demonstrated by the concentration by ⁽²⁴⁾ and colleagues, in which health workers have distinctive clinical and laboratory characteristics that differ from those of people in other occupations, necessitating special evaluation and biosafety designation. Finally, the main symptoms that appear in this study on Corona patients were Fever, headache and Emaciation while as reported in previous studies introduced ⁽²⁵⁾, the main three symptoms were fever, cough, and fatigue. As reported in past examinations introduced ⁽²⁶⁾. Fever, hacking, and tiredness were the predominant symptoms of COVID-19 sickness.

Conclusion:

In this study we explore the difference in the impact of some risk factors on contracting the disease and how similar and different symptoms of this virus are with others, paying special attention to the common pathological symptoms between patients and healthy people. Risk factors may differ from one society to another due to ethnic differences and differ from time to time due to the mutations and severity of the virus, Therefore, measures to protect or decreased the transmission of infection must be implemented in high-risk populations.

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